

CZU 342.71(478-476)

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5796542

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF CONSTITUTIONAL LEGAL REGULATION OF CITIZENSHIP OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS AND THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

Olga Vladimirovna VOLCHKEVICH

The article examines the content of the concepts of citizenship of the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova, methods of acquiring and terminating citizenship of these states, their differences in legislative regulation, the application of loss of citizenship on the territory of the Republic of Belarus and deprivation of citizenship in the Republic of Moldova. In the article, the author points out the grounds for acquiring citizenship of the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova. The author provides a comparative legal analysis of the institution of citizenship in the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova.

Key words: citizenship; admission to citizenship, restoration of citizenship, termination of citizenship; loss of citizenship; deprivation of citizenship; a threat; sovereignty.

ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА КОНСТИТУЦИОННО-ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ГРАЖДАНСТВА РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ И РЕСПУБЛИКИ МОЛДОВА

Ольга Владимировна ВОЛЧКЕВИЧ

В статье рассмотрено содержание понятий гражданства Республики Беларусь и Республики Молдова, способы приобретения и прекращения гражданства данных государств, их отличия в законодательном регулировании, применение утраты гражданства на территории Республики Беларусь и лишения гражданства в Республике Молдова. В статье автор указывает на основания приобретения гражданства Республики Беларусь и Республики Молдова. Автор приводит сравнительно-правовой анализ института гражданства в Республике Беларусь и Республике Молдова.

Ключевые слова: гражданство; прием в гражданство, восстановление в гражданстве, прекращение гражданства; утрата гражданства; лишение гражданства; угроза; суверенитет.

Citizenship is an essential attribute of the state's sovereignty.

New political realities have given rise to new problems, among which the problem of citizenship is of particular importance, since it directly affects the interests of the state and its population.

The dynamic changes in recent years have led to the emergence of completely new directions in the institution of citizenship. Therefore, their study is of great not only scientific, but also practical interest.

Finally, the relevance of the development of this topic is also predetermined by the fact that the problem of citizenship of the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova, due to their long stay in one state - the USSR, goes beyond the jurisdiction of each state, having an international legal aspect. Mapping national legislation on citizenship with the fundamental principles and norms of international law is one of the conditions for

its compliance with the standards adopted in the civilized world.

Of particular interest is the analysis of the norms of common law of the CIS (the CIS Charter, the CIS Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of May 26, 1995, the Declaration on International Obligations in the Field of Rights and Fundamental Freedoms in the CIS Countries of September 24, 1994, and other acts). It is also important to refer to the constitutional practice of the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova, which makes it possible to develop scientifically based measures, including within the framework of the CIS, to further improve the mechanism for regulating citizenship issues. In this regard, a good example is the recommendatory legislative act «On the agreed principles of citizenship regulation» developed by the CIS Interparliamentary Assembly of December 29, 1992, which establishes the basic principles of

citizenship, such as the right to citizenship (Article 2), equality of citizenship (Article 4), the right to appeal in court the violated powers in matters of citizenship (Art. 14) [1].

The object of the research is the institute of citizenship in the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova. Therefore, the subject of the study is to identify the most significant features, specific features, directions and trends in the development of citizenship of the Republic of Belarus and the Republic of Moldova. The methodological basis of the study is the comparative legal method.

General questions of citizenship were investigated by S.A. Avakyan, V. Ya. Kikot, O.E. Kutafin and N.M. Smorodin, O. I. Chupris, T. N. Mikhaleva. Some practical problems of acquiring and terminating citizenship were considered by S.N. Baburin, A.N. Golovistika, I.S. Daldinova, E.V. Mikhailova, M.M. Kharitonov, V.A. Yakovlev.

As a result of the collapse of the USSR, almost all post-Soviet states enshrined in the laws on citizenship the “zero option” of recognition of citizenship, when practically all persons, regardless of origin, social and property status, race and nationality and other grounds, living at the time these laws came into force, were automatically recognized as citizens of these states. At the same time, additional conditions were established in separate laws for the recognition of a person as a citizen of a particular state: the fact that a person does not have any other citizenship (Lithuania, Moldova, Uzbekistan, Ukraine); a person has a permanent place of residence on the territory of the country and a permanent place of work or other legal source of livelihood (Moldova); expression by a person of a desire to be a citizen (Moldova, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Ukraine), etc.

Currently, legal relations regarding the citizenship of the Republic of Moldova are regulated by Law No. LP1024 / 2000 dated 02.06.2000, with amendments dated 18.06.2020 (hereinafter - the Law on Moldovan Citizenship). In accordance with Part 1 of Art. 3 of the said law, the citizenship of the Republic of Moldova defines a permanent political and legal relationship between an individual and the Republic of Moldova, giving rise to mutual rights and obligations [2].

The definition of the concept of citizenship of the Republic of Belarus is different, significantly

different and regulated by Part 1 of Art. 1 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus No. 136-3 dated 01.08.2002, as amended on 10.12.2020 (hereinafter referred to as the Law on Citizenship of Belarus). Thus, citizenship of the Republic of Belarus is a stable legal relationship of a person with the Republic of Belarus, expressed in the totality of their mutual rights, duties and responsibilities, based on the recognition and respect for dignity, fundamental human rights and freedoms [3].

The grounds for acquiring citizenship of the Republic of Moldova in accordance with Art. 9 of the Law on Moldovan Citizenship are: by birth; due to adoption; upon repatriation; as a result of admission to citizenship; due to the restoration of the citizenship of the Republic of Moldova.

In Belarus, there are also five grounds for acquiring citizenship, however, with the listed grounds for acquiring Moldovan citizenship, only three coincide: by birth, as a result of admission, as a result of restoration. Also, citizenship of the Republic of Belarus can be acquired through registration and on other grounds provided for by international treaties.

In order to ensure national security and in accordance with Art. 20 of the Law on Moldovan Citizenship, state bodies will refuse to accept citizenship for those convicted of imprisonment for intentional offenses, having a criminal record or under investigation at the time of consideration of the application; who participated in the repressions; committed crimes international, military or against humanity; sowing national or racial hatred, spreading the ideas of fascism, chauvinism or Stalinism; carrying out activities aimed at undermining state security, public order, health and morality of the population; calling for violent change or overthrow of the social order enshrined in the Constitution Republic of Moldova; involved in terrorist activities; who are citizens of another state.

The Republic of Belarus also does not recognize dual citizenship and other forms of multiple citizenship. However, the grounds for termination of consideration of an application for acquiring citizenship in Belarus are deported, expelled from the Republic of Belarus, transferred to a foreign state; repeatedly (three or more times) during a calendar year was subjected to administrative penalties on the territory of the Republic of Belarus and the period after which it is considered not to

have been subject to administrative penalties has not expired; provided false information and (or) documents that do not meet the requirements of the law, including forged, fake or invalid; is in the military service, police service, security agencies, justice or other government agencies of a foreign state; died, declared missing by the court, or declared dead.

The grounds for termination of citizenship are also significantly different. The grounds for termination of citizenship of the Republic of Moldova are renunciation and deprivation of citizenship of the Republic of Moldova. Renunciation of citizenship is also denied to persons conscripted or in urgent military or alternative service. Deprivation of citizenship may also occur in relation to a person who has entered into a public office in another state without the knowledge and consent of the competent authorities of the Republic of Moldova.

Belarusian citizenship can be terminated as a result of exit and loss. The grounds for prohibiting the withdrawal and loss of citizenship differ significantly from those listed in the legislation of Moldova.

In conclusion, I would like to note that the general features of the regulation of legal relations of citizenship are enshrined in the legislation of our states. The impact of digitalization is one of the main prerequisites for the introduction on the territory of Belarus and Moldova of biometric passports as documents confirming citizenship.

Thus, the legislation of Belarus and Moldova on citizenship has similar features (non-recognition of multiple citizenship), however, the definition of the concept of citizenship, the grounds for its acquisition and termination are significantly different, as well as the consolidation of provisions on citizenship in the norms of the Constitution of our states. In the Republic of Belarus, citizenship is enshrined in Art. 10 of Section I of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus "Fundamentals of the Constitutional System" and enshrines the prohibition of deprivation of citizenship. Article 17 of Chapter I "General Provisions" of Section II "Fundamental Rights and Freedoms" of the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova contains norms on Moldovan citizenship and enshrines the prohibition of arbitrary deprivation of citizenship, which is fully consistent with Art. 15 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Bibliographic references

1. A recommendatory legislative act "On the agreed principles of citizenship regulation" [Electronic resource] // Electronic fund of legal and normative-technical documents. - Access mode: [https:// docs.cntd.ru/document / 901930781 /](https://docs.cntd.ru/document/901930781/). - Date of access: 25.11.2021.
2. Law on Citizenship of the Republic of Moldova [Electronic resource] // Parliament of the Republic of Moldova. - Access mode: [https:// www.legislationline.org/download/id / 9140 / file / MOL_on% 20citizenship_ru.pdf /](https://www.legislationline.org/download/id/9140/file/MOL_on%20citizenship_ru.pdf). - Date of access: 11/26/2021.
3. Law "On Citizenship of the Republic of Belarus" [Electronic resource] // World of Law. - Access mode: [http://world_of_law.pravo.by/ text.asp?RN=H10200136/](http://world_of_law.pravo.by/text.asp?RN=H10200136/). - Date of access: 11/26/2021.

About author

Olga Vladimirovna VOLCHKEVICH,

*lecturer at the Department
of Constitutional and International Law
Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs
of the Republic of Belarus,
6 Masherova Ave., 220005, Minsk, Belarus,
email:ovvolchkevich@mail.ru*